

Learning to Work While Homebound – The Effects of Remote Work on Job Performance during the Covid-19 Pandemic

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SUMMARY: The lockdown measures and population movement restrictions as a consequence of the Covid-19 pandemic as well forced the companies to implement the “Working from Home (WFH)” modality, this situation created an involuntary expansion that has incorporated different functions that cannot be correctly performed in a remote way. WFH characteristic have changed as a consequence of movement restrictions, the incorporation of administrative functions and the work schedule inflexibility, creating this way the rising job category “Working Homebound with Reduced Flexibility” (TCH, from its name in Spanish). This is the main reason why we have questioned its effect over the labor productivity and performance. The realized inquiries point out a learning process that has been established and does not decline the labor performance. Nevertheless, the TCH side effects on leadership, communication and organizational culture show ambiguous results, depending on the organization base conditions and the place where TCH is done. We are looking forward to creating a discussion over TCH, pointing out the motivation and commitment risks due to the impossibility to decide where, how and when to work, adding the management focus based on duties that decrease the motivation, creativity, and performance in long terms.

KEYWORDS: Covid-19 Pandemic, telework, labor performance, organizational learning, working homebound, performance management.

INTRODUCTION

Since March 2020, the Chilean society began to feel the havocs that Covid-19 Pandemic had been causing on a global scale since November 2019, when China revealed that a virus, unknown by then, was causing several breathing problems in the Wuhan citizens (Monasterio Blanco, 2021). Responding to the signs of the looming health crisis, the Chilean government ordered several measures to safeguard public health and to avoid a significant spread disease, which, by that time, were 238 cases on a national rate. The infection rate would remain stable until June 2020, when by the first time the barrier of one thousand daily infections was exceeded; from that point it would only be increasing until exceed the barrier of nine thousand daily infections on April 2021 (Data UC, 2021). As a prevent and control measures, schools and universities were closed, the companies which were not considered “essential” to the population had a restricted functioning, along with lockdowns and curfews to restrict population mobility and shifting. All these measures were fitting, activating, and deactivating according to the disease spread evolution on a national rate, being finally named “step by step gradual strategy” thrown on August 2020 (Chilean Government, 2021).

The impact of this situation was perceived in every corner of the Chilean society, in an economic, educational, sanitary, and physical and mental health, hitting also in the labor organizations, which were blocked to perform their functions in a regular way. This is the main reason why companies were forced to install the working from home system (WFH), with the twin purpose of keeping business running as well as to safeguard workers health (Conejo, 2020). This fact, triggered by the Covid-19 Pandemic meant a WFH expansion as a result of the incorporation of new kinds of industries and labor functions (eminently administrative), which, by the first time were added to this new labor agreement. It is worth to point out that, until then, WFH was showing an increasement in its implementation by the chilean companies, reaching out the 72% (Randstad, 2020).

The WFH expansion occurred in the year 2020 added new elements that modify the regular characteristics of remote work, telework and their multiple meanings. Those elements are related to the rigidity of the work schedule, the rigidity of the place

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where their functions are performed (mainly at home, according to the safeguard measures ordered by the authorities) and the rigidity of their functions, especially the administrative ones over the analytic and goal intended management functions. These elements modify the WFH nature itself, restricting the worker possibilities to choose where, how, and when to perform the job. Recent research are referred to the transformative constraints of WFH, proposing the rising category called “working homebound with reduced flexibility” (TCH), to better describe the characteristics of the expansion and remote work rigidity phenomenon on the Covid-19 Pandemic (Aliaga et al., 2021). It must be pointed out that the WFH expansion phenomenon was not only registered on a local basis, but also (just like the pandemic) it set globally (OIT, 2020; Raisiene et al., 2020; Thulin et al., 2019). In this context, the WFH particularities were added to the mobility restrictions and safeguard measures to prevent population disease spreading. Related to his phenomenon, in Chile the number of companies which were used to adding any kind of remote work (mostly known as telework), went from 46% in 2019 to a 95% in 2020 (InvestChile, 2020). This unprecedented situation in the labor history of the country has had consequences and has generated every kind of changes, one of them has been reflected on the TCH effect over the workers performance. In our view a relevant matter, because it implies as organizations, in this kind of forced rehearsal, as the people who are implied on its performance, can conduct a thorough assessment based on scientific research that shed new lights over this phenomenon, allowing them to identify its own particularities and, along with it, to implement measures to its maintenance, adjustment and/or permanent modification in the new kinds of labor forms of relations which came to stay. For those reasons, we have designed an inductive research over the working homebound effects in the workers labor performance, specifically in a logistics company in Chile. For that purpose, we used the methodological approach of Grounded Theory (qualitative inductive method), in order to know deeply what is happening with this particular phenomenon inside the studied organization. For the collection of data, we have designed a questionnaire to develop deep interviews, which were applied on 21 organization members. This questionnaire had 30 questions to inquire about the technological and connectivity, organizational, and leader and communication among other issues. The data collection for this research produced fourteen taped interview hours, which were transcribed into MS Word, in order to be analyzed through the Atlas.ti system. By following the stages of the chosen qualitative analysis, we went from initial coding, the generation of code groups, analysis webs and concept categories to the development of a grounded theory which explains this particular phenomenon and shed lights about what is happening in a specific level and from it is possible to contrast the information with some other research in order to create bigger and better thoughts about this topic.

TELEWORK ART STATE AND ITS EFFECTS ON LABOR PERFORMANCE

When speaking about syntax and etymology, the word “Telework” is composed with the noun “work” which comes from the ancient English word “wyrkan”, which is referred to an action development that requires constant physical or mental effort. Also, the Greek prefix “tele”, “distant” or “remote” (Lozada Elizalde, 2016, p. 9). Expanding the foundations of its original meaning, this concept is mainly referred to the realization of a sustained effort, eminently mental, which is made in a remote way through TICs and is mainly related to paid work by a third party (OIT, 2020). As to the notion of “Telework” or “Remote Work” (one of the many used concepts to refer to this phenomenon), its origins are found in 1970 in the United States, when the Oil Shock occurred, forcing companies and the government to bring mitigating measures to deal with the upcoming complications, as much in an economic as social level due to the fact of scarcity of fossil fuels (UNED, n.d.). In order to ensure the business and operations continuity, some companies added the option of developing remote work, especially for those employees whose functions were appropriated (mental work) and had the technological resources and digital competences to develop their tasks; as a result of these measures, the times of movement to/from work decreased and consequently workers were more efficient. Those measures pointed out that the employees should develop their duties from their place of living (*working from home*), as well as in the company facilities which were near to their homes (*telecommuting*), even if this place was not the common place of work (Chávez, 2020, p. 2).

Next on, we introduce an overview of the investigations that are referred to the WFH effects on the labor performance, in its different dimensions and presenting the results that perceive the paradigm of Telework and its ambiguous consequences. To be able to accomplish this “art state” review on this matter, we focused on those scientific publications that show the results from investigations whose key words are related to “*Working from Home*”, “WFH”, “*Trabajo desde el Hogar*”, “*Trabajo remoto desde el Hogar*” and “*Telework*”. All these key words were combined with words such as “Performance”, “Labor Performance”, “*Desempeño Laboral*”, “*Productividad*”, “*Job Productivity*”. The scientific publications that match with our key word search, in its different combinations, were tracked during a wide period of time that goes from the pre-Covid-19 era, from year 2020 onwards and furthermore during the Covid-19 Global Pandemic (2019 and 2020). With this purpose, the searches were made in different

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digital platforms that compile and spread scientific publications ideas, such as Research.net, Google Scholars, Academia.edu and Scielo.

POSITIVE EFFECTS

The specialized literature points out multiple positive effects that comes from the WFH experience, which not only impact on the labor performance and productivity, but also in micro, macro and meso dimensions. Among the announced positive effects, it is possible to appreciate: 1) labor performance and productivity's improvement; 2) job satisfaction's increase; 3) labor creativity's increase; 4) employees' safety increase; 5) business management during the times of crisis; 6) balance between work/personal life and/or family time; 7) promote digital skills development; and 8) community benefits increase.

The eight positive effects pointed out by the investigations, at the time, are related to several intervening variables that make possible every result as a WFH consequence. Among the main variables are: 1) Employees' characteristics, skills, and personal competences, such as time management, discipline, self-motivation, and goal-oriented work (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020; Bosua et al., 2013; Dima et al., 2019; Nakrosiene et al., 2019; Vega et al., 2015; Vyas & Butakhieo, 2020). 2) Goal-oriented performance management (Bosua et al., 2013; Saputra et al., 2013). 3) Appropriated IT factors (TICs and IT) (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020). 4) Organization characteristics (Trust based culture) (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020; Dima et al., 2019). 5) Home's workplace characteristics (material aspects) (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020; Nakrosiene et al., 2019; Vyas & Butakhieo, 2020). 6) Less interference due to the lesser time to communicate with coworkers (Nakrosiene et al., 2019). 7) Effective remote/digital leadership styles (Dima et al., 2019; Saputra et al., 2020). 8) Family group characteristics (FWI & WIF) (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020).

The referred intervenient variables are determined by the telework's "base factors" (Nicholson & Baruch, 1997). Specially, in those investigations that shown positive findings on the WFH effects over the labor performance, "characteristics and personal competences" are mentioned predominantly, being referred by six out of the seven reviewed investigations (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020; Bosua et al., 2013; Dima et al., 2019; Nakrosiene et al., 2019; Vega et al., 2016; Vyas & Butakhieo, 2020). On the second place are the factors related to "organizational characteristics" which are referred in four of those investigations (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020; Bosua et al., 2013; Dima et al., 2019; Saputra et al., 2020). The factors related to the "family group and home conditions affecting the WFH modality" are referred in three investigations (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020; Nakrošienė et al., 2019; Vyas & Butakhieo, 2020). Lastly, the factors associated to the "ITs infrastructure" and the "work characteristics and its similarity with WFH modality" are mentioned in only two and one investigations respectively (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020; Bosua et al., 2013). The lower amount of references in these last factors mainly comes to show that in the first Covid-19 Global Pandemic's period, the conditions related to ITs and also with the characteristics of telework made in a remote way, are correctly incorporated to the WFH functioning, this, because currently the ITs have presented a wide development and infiltration in homes and companies and also it can be presumed that the characteristics of jobs developed in a remote way, somehow are adjusted with the regular remote work characteristics. Yet, we have previously referred that the WFH expansion and the addition to it of administrative workers kind doing their jobs in their usual work time, are one of the reasons on the changing nature that turns it into TCH.

NEGATIVE EFFECTS

The recent investigations shown a bigger amount of WFH negative effects (nine) when comparing with the positive effects (eight), related as much to the labor performance and productivity as in different individual, organizational and community dimensions. The main negative consequences are: 1) affects the quality of life and workers wellbeing; 2) emotional impact: loneliness, irritability, worriedness and guilt; 3) labor performance and productivity decrease; 4) creates psychological negative effects: mental fatigue and work overload; 5) creates family-work interferences (FIW); 6) creates work-family interferences (WIF); 7) creativity and initiative decrease due to the excessive supervisor's intromission (digital/remote leadership); 8) social sustainability diminished as a consequence of the negative effects on people and their family group, and 9) affects the balance between work and personal life (life quality).

The mentioned negative effects are related to several intervenient variables that determine the results in a macro, meso and micro level. Among them it is possible to distinguish: 1) Time management (Thulin et al., 2019a). 2) Lack of labor support (Mann & Holdsworth, 2003). 3) Multiplicity of roles during the telework (Bhattacharya & Mittal, 2020; Solís, 2017). 4) Digital/remote leadership (Singh et al., 2017; Solís, 2017). 5) Psychosocial factors due to isolation (Venegas, Tresierra & Leyva Pozo, 2020a). 6) Blurring limits between work and personal life (Bhattacharya & Mittal, 2020; Mann & Holdsworth, 2003). 7) Bigger effort and work overload (Mann & Holdsworth, 2003; Thulin et al., 2019b). and 8) Organizational communication issues (Singh et al., 2017).

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When investigating about the WFH “basic factors” which are present on the analyzed research’ results, it is possible to note that “family group” and “home conditions affecting on the WFH modality” are predominant, being present in the analysis proposed by five investigations (Bhattacharya & Mittal, 2020; Mann & Holdsworth, 2003; Solís, 2017; Thulin et al., 2019b; Venegas Tresierra & Leyva Pozo, 2020a). Another relevant base factor in this type of investigation is related to “work characteristics and its similarity with the WFH modality”, being mentioned by four investigations (Bhattacharya & Mittal, 2020; Mann & Holdsworth, 2003; Thulin et al., 2019b; Venegas Tresierra & Leyva Pozo, 2020a). There is also a great predominance of the base factors related to the “organizational characteristics that promote the WFH modality (culture, structure and results management)”, being announced by three investigations (Mann & Holdsworth, 2003; Singh et al., 2017; Solis, 2017). On the last level appears the base factor related to the “characteristics and personal competences”, being referred by only two investigations (Thulin et al., 2019b; Venegas Tresierra & Leyva Pozo, 2020a).

We find interesting the fact that in none of the investigations we have analyzed about the negative effects of WFH on the labor performance, are mentioned the base factors associated to “ITs infrastructure (ITCs)”. This is why, we point out this dimension is appropriated to develop an investigation on this matter, because this is not quite analyzed when speaking about the negative effects that can affect the WFH modality and labor performance, despite the fact that the specialized literature has been emphatic in stating that ITCs are essential to develop work duties in a remote way. In this regard, is conclude that the ITCs factor is not mentioned in the investigations because it is not an essential condition to develop remote work, therefore the investigations start from the base that if there is remote work, it is because the ITCs are correctly incorporated and working. Despite that, this accelerated and forced expansion phenomenon of working from home during the times of Covid-19 in Chile, also implies that exist some organizations and people that do not have correctly incorporated and/or developed the technological areas, affecting the results of the remote work when speaking about labor performance and productivity.

Summarizing the review and discussion of the investigations results that mention, among others, the effects of remote work on the labor performance, it is possible to appreciate that the consequences of WFH modality creates ambiguous effects, reporting as much positive as negative effects over the same variables and dimensions of people, work, and their environment. This phenomenon is a consequence of the way in which the base factors are present and adapting in each case. This is why is possible to point out that there is an ambiguity or paradox of the WFH modality as much on the labor performance as in other dimensions of labor issues and its impact on individuals and communities.

QUESTIONS AND INVESTIGATION OBJECTIVES

In view of the above, our concern related to TCH and its impact over the labor performance, we have proposed the following question about it:

Has the TCH impacted on the performance and fulfilling the job objectives of workers who have participated on this modality inside of the studied organization?

Based on the previous question, our principal objective is to understand and to explain the TCH impact over the studied organization workers labor performance.

From the main objective we can extract to specific objectives related to:

- 1) To know the impact of TCH on the objective’s fulfillment on the position and its performance from workers who have realized and not yet realized jobs under this kind of labor contract.
- 2) To explain the impact of TCH on the objective’s fulfillment on the position and its performance from workers who have realized and no yet realized jobs under this kind of labor contract.

INVESTIGATION METHOD

By the nature of our concern, we set out an investigation with a non-experimental design (without data manipulation and by observing the phenomenon in the place where it occurs), of transactional kind (observation of the phenomenon in a determined space of time) in a descriptive and exploratory way (Hernandez Sampieri et al., 2014). To know the TCH phenomenon and its effect on workers labor performance in a logistic company in Chile, we used the qualitative inductive method called “Grounded Theory” (GT from now on), with the purpose to generate an explanatory model of human behavior which is mainly based on the compiled data in the place where actions take place (Aigner, 2012). Laperriere (1997) says that the GT objective is not to produce an exhaustive representation of a phenomenon, but to elaborate a concerning pertinent theory (Raymond, 2005), also called substantive theory (Hernández Sampieri et al., 2014, p. 473). The GT involves the progressive identification and the meanings categories integration from data. At the time, the process of categories identification and data integration (as a method) and its product as a particular theory. The GT as a method guides us about how to identify the categories, how to link the categories and

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how to establish relationships between them. The GT as a theory is the final product of this process which creates a summarized conceptual framework which explains what is happening when speaking about the studied phenomenon (Willing, 2013, p. 70).

The company we chose for the investigation is a Chilean company in the logistic field, which has the particularity of have never implemented telework from home until the Covid-19 Global Pandemic, starting in that way in March 2019.

When GT is used as an investigation method, the researchers do not start the project with preconceived theory unless their purpose is to complement, to deepen and/or widen an existing theory. Moreover, the findings start in a specific studying area, making the data rise from the theory. It is assumed that the derived theory (partial, restricted) is closer to the studied situation or phenomenon than the traditional non-grounded theory. Due to the GT is based in the data collected, is more probable it generates new knowledge, increases the understanding of this phenomenon, and supplies a meaningful guide on how to react (Strauss & Corbin, 2002, pp. 21–22). Bringing the words from the authors: “To theorize is the act of building [...] from data, an explanatory diagram which in a systematic way merges several concepts by means of sentences that point out the relationships. A theory allows more than to understand something or painting a colorful art piece. It gives the opportunity to users to explain and predict happenings, which gives guides for the action” (Strauss & Corbin; 2002, p. 36).

- **Sample and data collection:** the used sample to the investigation are twenty-one workers who are part of the studied organization, these people develop multiple functions as much administrative as analytics, of supervision or leadership, and also management and running. All these people who participated in the findings were developing their duties in a remote way when were interviewed. The duration of each interview lasted between 30 minutes and an hour. The criteria to select the interview participants was based in the variability of their functions and positions in the company who by the way were developing their work while homebound at the time of the investigation. It is worth to point out this criterion is not looking for any sample representativity when speaking in a statistic way, but as a structural sample with a saturated sample. This means, to perform deep interviews to workers from different areas and hierarchical levels in the company, until reaching the point where interviewed are no longer giving new or important information to be deepened and keep going with more findings.

The period in which the investigation took place with the data collection, went from December 2020 and March 2021. To be able to develop the interviews, before we met every participant, we sent them out a form where they signed a formal and informed consent about the importance of this interview and clarifying its scope, after that, we applied 30 questions to them to find the IT and connectivity, organizational, leadership and communication aspects, among others. The interviews were done through ITCs such as Zoom and Google Meets, according with the availability of each interviewed. The data collection process delivered fourteen hours of video and audio material, which were completely transcribed to a text type format MS Word through the transcription service Sonix.ai. Once the interview transcription was completed, we started to analyze the information through the Atlas.ti system (ninth version).

- **Analysis procedures:** once the first interviews were video-taped and transcribed to text, we continued with the data analysis through the initial coding process, which was getting bigger at the time the sample grew. In this initial phase, we could refine even more the base questionnaire to be able to scope more information about the concept interpretations arose during this first stage. As the coding process was growing, through all the data reviewing and re-codification on the first's interviews, and along with it the analysis was delivering a bigger clarity and comprehension level on this phenomenon, were developed a total of 144 codes (among in live codes and developed by the researchers' codes).

In an advanced stage of the analysis, just like in many stages of the qualitative analysis process developed, it meant to move between the coding, the analysis, the interpretation, and the data re-coding, we developed seven memos with interpretative information coming from the data working and the questions which popped out in the process. These memos were mixed, some were shaped like new questions, others were related to the theoretical characteristics in which the reflection process and the bigger understanding of this phenomenon were based. The memos information allowed us to develop bigger findings and also to provide content and conceptual categories that were arisen during the transitions of the analysis made on its first steps.

Having reached a higher clarity grade over the data and the interrelation between codes, we started to group them according to their characteristics. Later, we applied a data analysis over the code groups that were put together according to their characteristics and co-relations among them, which highlighted a bigger and deeper dimension of the studied

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phenomenon, creating nine conceptual categories that were reinforced according to the data re-analysis and also with the add of new questions and findings to the theoretical sample, in order to complete the properties of every category according with the information given by the participants, creating the sample saturation.

In the final stage of the data analysis and interpretation process, leading to the substantial theory development, we used the web generation of the codes of each category to understand their characteristics and individual properties, as well as the interrelation of the conceptual category group, giving shape to the GT final result, which allows us to understand and to explain the studied phenomenon.

RESULTS

As a result of the analysis process, we developed a substantial theory or grounded theory (GT) which explains the studied phenomenon. The GT is made of nine categories or conceptual dimensions correlated among them which are exposed in a web scheme that allows us to understand and to explain the TCH phenomenon and its impact on the labor performance. In the next sections, we will introduce the resultant GT and we will review each one of the conceptual dimensions composing it, by referring their main properties and characteristics.

1. Learning how to sail on telework.

The GT central category developed is related to the dimension we call “learning how to sail on telework”, which comes from a live code found during the data analysis and interpretation:

“[...] learning how we could sail it because, after all, if you as their boss tell them: hey, try to disconnect yourself from work earlier today, because yesterday you worked afterhours, I realized you sent an email at that hour. Finally, one can not force them. At the end, it is up to them. But there you are, playing with the topics prioritization” (interview n°1).

This category is closely related to the nature of the telework expansion and the imperative Covid-19 Global Pandemic situation that forced the investigated organization to apply the WFH modality for the first time, a pioneer experience as much for the company as for most of its workers. The following, there are some referred codes that are a part of this category:

First telework experience: *“[...] this is my first telework experience. Yes, I have been here, at my house since March”* (interview n°12).

“No, no, no, no. I have never worked from home before. I’m kind of restless there, I always like to go out, you’ll understand, a person like me... from the X Generation, this is how we like it, we like that routine where you go out to the street [...]” (interview n°15).

The WFH modality, being a novelty and with no precedent experience inside the labor organization, ended in improvisation situations during the adaptation process into the new way of working:

Improvisation at the beginning of telework: *“No, no, no, no, no, no, I have no memory of this being told to us, not to me at least, none of them came to explain to me what was this about”* (interview n°1).

Telework adaptation: *“Well, the meaning has changed a lot since March 2020. At the beginning it was super ambiguous, too hard to understand and deal with. Today, telework is a tool for me. It suits perfectly with our duties. Until today at least”* (interview n°17).

As the time goes by, and as the pandemic was getting more serious in Chile, a WFH adaptation state came slowly, based on the acquired learning that allowed the creation of new work habits, the development of self-management and time-management competences by the organization members; all of that ended in the thought that “it was possible to work from home!” (Live code):

Learnings: *“We had to get along with the idea of lockdowns due to the Covid-19 Global Pandemic, we had to learn how to not be going to the office. We had to adapt to the same. Telework. I think this is one of the main learnings, the ability to quickly adapt oneself”* (interview n°21).

Creating the telework habit: *“[...] because inside this schedule one’s doing, creating the habit, it also helped you to understand that in that time frame you were not having any meetings. And if you had any, it was because you decided it”* (interview n°1).

It was possible to work from home! : *“[...] I do a chronogram of how much time I should take on this. I work related to that, because I say ‘ok, if it takes me 4 hours to download data, I will be those four hours in front of my PC! But if I see I have longer or shorter time to do it, I manage it, it will depend on the reality too, as how I am living that moment”* (interview n°2).

“Today, we have demonstrated that we do produce. Then, could we go back? I think the answer is no, there is no need” (interview n°13).

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Summarizing, the so-called category “learning how to sail on telework” becomes a fundamental piece in the studied phenomenon, this due to the fact that it allows the understanding of characteristics such as novelty, adaptation, learning, work habit creation, self-management, time management and finally, the conviction that it was possible to develop remote work.

2. Organizational learning.

This theoretical dimension is associated to the central category “learning how to sail on telework” as it is the synthesis of the whole process lived by the organization when facing the uncertainty itself about the pandemic and the TCH effects, which took us to the conviction that it indeed was possible to work from home. Related to this, we understand the organizational learning as the organization behavior modification based on new knowledge, skills or abilities given by its members (Chiavenato, 2009, p. 488). Let’s see their main codes:

Pandemic uncertainty itself: “[...] I feel like that was the most important, to have the pandemic uncertainty itself. The physical space to be able to separate it from personal life and also mentally to be able to separate the working life from your house, your home. That, those three points I think, are the most important, I can not remember any other right now. How did I learn to do it? I think your body itself helps you, your organism feels like telling you are not doing ok” (interview n° 17).

Working homebound (TCH): “[...] when the pandemic started to become real, and stronger, in May, June and July, there was not much to do but to be at home, locked. This used to happen a lot, the boredom, and to have nothing more to do than stay home, made us stay focused on work for many hours, which was the only obligation we had” (interview n°2)

The properties from above, firstly, are a consequence of the raising of a unique telework perception, which will be delimited by the Pandemic and TCH negative effects. Related to the organizational culture, which we understand as the belief and presumptions that have demonstrated to be the appropriated answer to the organization surviving problems, as much in their inner integration as in its external organization (Schein, 1998. Pp. 23-24). The studied organization reflects the classic work on site model and the fulfillment of labor schedules. During this adaptation process, the telework culture arises, as a result of the successful learning and the addition of new ways to react and to respond to the pandemic issues, which ended in a positive perception about telework:

Telework perception: “Well, I don’t know if I said I before, but I [...] had a really bad time here, locked. I used to get up working, I used to go to sleep working. I could not create the division between my work and my family life. It took me a lot, and actually, I still have trouble to do so. (interview n°3).

“at first obviously, this created a trauma, but after a couple weeks, maybe in the third or fourth week you just start to get used to this new way of working and that it has been good, because I have been able, maybe not in person, but I manage to keep the same or even higher communicational level among the people I have to work with”. (interview n°4)

Organizational culture: “Since I came here, which is not long, it have always been like this, directly with them. So, they are used to it. Just picture that from one day to another you tell them that the HHRR people are not here anymore to answer their questions, doubts or many times they just came along to talk and tell you a little about their life, like, when they became grandparents, parents or that they went on vacation. Sometimes, those situations are really healthy for an organization. Because, not in everyone of the organizations this happens and that is what keeps the workers in a wellness state, in this case, the inner costumer.” (interview n°7)

Telework culture: “to not have this, this habit changing a lot, the time schedule, the space and eh a telework culture. Finally, this company runs through meetings, this is a meeting company eh, and unless it is a whole company, there must be a culture about how to organize the meetings, because some workers are going to be at the place of work while others will be at their houses via telework [it means a group which work in person and other group working in a remote way]” (interview n°1).

When going deep in this organizational learning dimension, mainly in the telework culture phenomenon, we can see that the organization went from being against remote work, that was possible to note according to the jokes they used to make about the people working this way, which created in the remote workers the feeling of being “chased”. To our perception, this situation is linked to the organizational culture which is focused on the working on site (based on the time schedule and tasks fulfillment):

Making jokes about people working in a remote way: “then between my partners, just saying, the people working with me, all of them were physically working. I was the only one working from home and also Jesús [she means a coworker], who was going and coming and that was a constant joke when you called them about work, they would say to me or call me and if I did not get the phone because I was somewhere... they would start: were you sleeping? Are you on your pj’s? have you showered yet?” (interview n°1).

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Feeling chased: *“Interviewer: it looks super interesting to me how you use the expression “I feel chased”. When you bring that up, do you mean you have to be able to demonstrate that you are working; do you feel like there is a sense, I do not know, from the headship, that the time is not being used to complete your tasks? Is that what you mean?”*

“Interviewed: That is what one thinks, of course. That feeling that maybe they are thinking that that person is lying down, lying down, and connecting from time to time. But that is all. That is why one tries to stay online, isn’t one? Obviously, a hundred percent focused, without no one noticing.” (interview n°4).

As the time goes by and as a consequence to the difficulties that the organization was going through due to the pandemic and the TCH effects, a bigger efficiency was developed in the function’s performance, the time management, and the availability of the correct physical spaces to perform telework, all those effects can be understood as a better work organization. To that is possible to add a key element inside the organization, the learning of “being able to stand in one other’s shoes”, which makes visible a change among the staff:

Efficiency and work organization: *“Interviewed: No, one has to be more efficient because it is fast. Plus, the fact of trying to balance my work with my personal life so my daughter does not feel kept away, then efficiency! Since eight o’clock in the morning until two and a half in the afternoon that is when I am with my baby! [she laughs when she says this, she was reacting to her own words] efficiency, efficiency! Ha ha ha ha, if not, nothing works. She has lunch late; I do not finish my lunch. Sometimes, it has happened that is quarter to three and I am still online, finishing... then... [the interviewer interrupts].”*

“Interviewer: Yes. So, how do you develop a pattern and a specific time schedule? You have to make sure things... [the interviewed interrupts]”

“Interviewed: that everything fits!”

“Interviewer: right.”

“Interviewed: yeah, everything has to fit so I can finish” (interview n°12).

To stand in one other’s shoes: *“I think that more than solutions, there is understanding, and they are capable to stand in your shoes, by saying: hey, you know that in the distribution center sometimes we had connection issues, how is it not possible to have connectivity issues from home? And also, the light bill... (interview n°6).*

Summarizing, the organizational learning is demonstrated through the transition or adaptation process lived by the workers, who lived the critical stages of the uncertainty and the TCH effects, which implied a negative perception about telework, and that was also reinforced by the working in person culture, punctuality, and the daily tasks. This critical organizational learning stage was marked by the jokes that the workers who were developing their functions in person made about those who were working in a remote way or via telework. As the learning curve was getting flat, the organization arrived at a better stage of work and efficiency management, which ended in a cultural change that starts in the point in which the organization workers start to stand in someone else’s shoes, especially when there is the idea that in fact it is possible to work from home. This kind of learning becomes valid when facing a huge problem like the organization is doing, the cultural change gets stronger in the group.

3. Organizational Communication.

A fundamental dimension inside this remote work scheme, in any of its shapes, is directly related to the organizational communication in its formal and informal ways, which depend on ITCs to be able to work in every dimension (Chiavenato, 2009, p. 321). Inside the organization in which we studied the TCH phenomenon we found an adaptation and an agreement process when speaking about organizational communication that, as the TCH effects, shows ambiguities related to provide timely and transversal access to the required information by the workers, as in the communicational inefficiency that responds to the adaptation made by the organization during its transition to a remote work way. :

Organizational communication: *“Is super important because at the end is like I said, I work with people and I work with supervisors, that actually if I stay informed about what is going on, I can go out and face some event along with them, ehm better prepared, somehow” (interview n°7).*

Timely information’s access: *“Interviewer: have you had trouble when trying to get the information you need to develop your work correctly?”*

“Interviewed: No, I have not had trouble by now. It may have been in some cases, I do not know, yesterday, for example, my internet connection was awful, I do not know what happened, I do not know if it was a country issue, city issue maybe, I do not know, but the truth is that I had a really bad signal, but it did not stop me for doing my job.” (interview n°20).

Communication inefficiency: *“When looking backwards is possible to note that before there were not so many meetings, and you were in person. Then I do not know, for example, the boys sometimes... my office was a little away from their”*

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workplaces, but they used to call me at my extension and said [name of the interviewed] could I go 5 minutes? Yeah, sure! you know? They used to go to my desk, showed me what they were doing, it was ok. But now I feel like they are just getting in line to communicate it. I was there before, I had all the time in the world by then, but I do not anymore” (interview n°13).

As a characteristic of this organizational communicational process in a remote way, we found this is made based in two ambiguous properties, on one hand, the information timely access, and in the other hand, the communication inefficiency. About the first characteristic, its properties are focused in “not losing the connection with people”, and to generate “closeness despite the distance”, which is part of a learning process about “finding how to relate to others” formally (e-mails) and informally (WhatsApp messages):

Not to lose the connection with people: *“at the beginning it was hard to place yourself at home, those kinds of things that were more like domestic communication, but I think today it helps a lot, even to be able to set meetings among several teams and in some cases way easier than when it was in person” (interview n°21).*

Closeness despite the distance: *“what I mean, the only investment here is the physical contact. If it is put below, we kind of have contact, we spoke or greet each other every morning at eight thirty. When we start, we give us all a “good morning”, we speak about what we are doing, and whatever, we share some important information, what is going to happen, and we tell everybody. There is an engineer team, there is always feedback, contact and knowing about what is going on with the others.” (interview n°16).*

Finding out how to relate to others: *“it was not here all the time, but it has been here the last five years, is true. So, for example, some regions we constantly interact with, uhm we had technology, but we have just discovered it and we have discovered too that it was so much easier to reach a distribution center instead of doing it by phone or cellphone somehow. And by interacting through this technology, it was also like discover; discover that deep down you can still relate to others without being in the same place” (interview n°1).*

Whatsapp groups: *“Interviewer: is everyone in that group?*

Interviewed: exactly, they are all in the same group. So, there is, I do not know, is not a very active group, we do not talk all day long, but we do talk about important and relevant topics, I do not know, COVID measures or what is going on, I do not know, in Punta Arenas, what is going on in Coquimbo, or we here in Santiago or I do not know. Good morning, today we are going to start the data downloading, I do not know. Just by giving a COVID protocol example. So, there is the space where everything is informed. All and the same information for everyone.” (interview n°7).

When speaking about the organizational communicational inefficiency, its characteristics are related to the “meetings abuse”, the lack of information due to the fact of not being present” as much as the “lose of informal communication”:

Meeting abuse: *“At the beginning we had an hour a day where we used to get along. After that we realized that with all this, the telework, the meetings and the use of Teams and Zoom [ITCs used by the organization]. At the beginning it was super exaggerated, and we had our schedule full of meetings” (interview n°17).*

Lack of information due to the fact of not being present: *“The thing is I had to ways, one of them was the information I got from my bosses, which was always on the right time and moment, and the other is the information I had to spread with these supervisors I work with that I have talked to you about, that was more complicated, it was later, uhm there was the need of insisting because you were not there. So there started what I said was necessary to be there, because if we are separated is so much hard to keep control. That control is a bit lost” (interview n°7).*

Loss of informal communication: *“I think that in the labor scenario it has been easy for me. But I do miss the partnership, that is what I miss the most. [...] I, I was one of those people who greeted everyone, who new all the departments, who asked favors, who used to go everywhere, who used to get all the guys together, I was the one who organized the meeting. So, I miss those lunches with my coworkers, those cigarettes, going shopping after lunch. I do not know” (interview n°18).*

Summarizing, due to the fact that communication is essential to reach the harmony and consistency in people behavior, this dimension represents a fundamental element of the remote work. The analyzed case, it is characterized by the way the organization makes the adjustment to communicate to every member during the pandemic times. Due to the fact that this is a bigger adaptation process, some ambiguous communication characteristics related to the learning acquisition of the studied organization are shown.

4. IT aspects and digital skills.

As we referred in the theoretical dimension “organizational communication”, the essential base conditions for this to be successful to the remote work development are mainly associated to ITCs, along with the correct internet connection and the according IT

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support from the organization. These are the three basic elements on IT levels to the work development. Which is why, of being present, they allow the timely information access and the correct remote functions performing:

Good internet connection: *“to use it as internet. In my particular case, I never had any problem. Even if my internet connection went down, I can still do my job or to accomplish my part of the job without interruptions. I had one or two unstable connections, but after that they gave us those cellphones that look like internet modems so we can still connect, so I had no trouble to work”* (interview n°7).

Bad internet connection: *“uhm, the truth is that I think that the only missing thing, generally speaking, is to have an individual internet connection, our own, the one we can work from home with. Is like the only tool that should exist for those who are working homebound, does not matter if it is all week or three days a week when you are home. But it is like essential, because one know that there is not connection intermittence, unlike the internet we have at home, because at home we are all connected”* (interview n°19).

ITs: *“easier, I think, because they are in the same TEAMS [referring to the TEAMS Microsoft system], the WhatsApp’s themselves, I think that due to these networks there is less personal contact it becomes faster. For example, I send a message to the guys, some supervisor answers sometime after. For example, when I was in the warehouse and at the time, I needed someone, it would be easier to look for them. But there is a problem too. Instead, now I send a message and give me an answer, it is easier to coordinate, I do not know”* (interview n°2).

Accurate IT support: *“No, no, because I when they sent me home with a cellphone and a computer. The computer was in poor conditions, and they changed it. After that, they changed it again and at the end they decided to send me a new one. So, they gave me an institutional cellphone so I could be able to stay online, and a new computer”* (interview n°9).

To count on the accurate IT elements to the correct performance of the communication and information functions of people who are working in this remote way, is a must to the successful implementation of this new kind of labor agreement. Along with it, the digital skills, and the competences for the ITs right use and benefit by the workers, is another ground element, which has been affected by the lack of training at the beginning of the homebound adaptation process, which involved that workers had to discover ITCs by their own, and slowly took them to develop the capacities for using IT tools:

Lack of training: *“Interviewer: did you have any formal training to use this tool and the software you use for telework? Interviewed: No, in fact short ago I participated in an intermediate Excel course, but it was like..., it was my idea, so I could know how much I knew. I also know some Excel, I have a basic computational level, a little, a little bit more than basic. I am not extraordinary either, but I had the knowledge, I had the knowledge, and everything related to SAP. One is learning by oneself”* (interview n°6).

ITCs discovery: *“Interviewer: sure! These remote meetings...*

Interviewed: it was not here all the time, but it has been here the last five years, is true. So, for example, some regions we constantly interact with, uhm we had technology, but we have just discovered it and we have discovered too that it was so much easier to reach a distribution center instead of doing it by phone or cellphone somehow. And by interacting trough this technology, it was also like discover; discover that deep down you can still relate to others without being in the same place” (interview n°1).

The development of abilities to the use of IT tools: *“Interviewer: from these tools, has the learning been there because you started to look for what was this about? Or have you had any kind of formal training according to what is possible to do via Zoom, Teams or similar?”*

Interviewed: Nothing formal, only by clicking in the app, but I am used to search and looking through the pages and apps I have, I am kind of curious with these things, so I am also learning fast” (interview n°2).

It is possible to conclude, according to the investment in IT aspects and digital skills, that the organization had and provided the accurate IT elements to the workers function development in a remote way, as the appropriated ITCs. Nevertheless, the lack of training to the abilities development that allow the correct use of technologies by the workers showed some differences, which made the people to look for information in a way they could manage these technologies, affecting the correct performance of their functions, due to the fact that it mainly depends on the individual capacities to get used to and to acquire the missing knowledge to the correct technologies use and applications. Specially, the workers who develop administrative work and with repetitive tasks were the ones who had more trouble to cover these issues when comparing with those workers whose functions are more analytics and interpretative.

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5. Digital leadership.

The leadership dimension during the TCH stage, also called remote or digital leadership (Saputra et al., 2020, p. 254), is a phenomenon that gives key importance to the GT arising from the data, this, due to the leader role is related to a formal authority such as the boss or a supervisor in the analyzed organization, implies a working style phenomenon based in the results management in order to reach the company goals, supporting it in a constant and timely labor feedback. In this way, the team members keep together and informed about how they are developing their jobs and what are the goals they have to reach as much individually as collectively. Among the properties of this kind of leadership, along with guiding and promoting the use of platforms and digital technologies in the team, it is also encouraging the group participation and the integration of new ideas and proposals to solve problems about how to develop a job, to keep the team timely informed about each particular situations, which at the time, creates this group integration perception. All this, in the migration to digital platforms context and the pursuit of team sustainability based on the correct performance of the remote functions:

Digital leadership: *“I think everything must impact, in a positive or negative way, but it has to make an impact, I feel like... As I was saying, I feel that when there is not communication there is not... there is no way to look for solutions, so, uhmmm, what we have tried to do with, let’s say, with my bosses, is to try to have a better communication, starting from the base of it being “personal” right!, close to the person, and then, try to talk about the labor topics and if there is anything to improve, logically we are in that path, constantly, we have to be there constantly” (interview n°8).*

Working for goals, not to meet a time schedule: *“I think before we used to do a lot, every day or three times a week, but it was a lot [speaking about team meetings]. I mean, I believe Mondays was the ideal. Is where we organize, ok, we have all this for this week, and when I see that there is one of them not going forward. Uhm, uhm, I tell him: hey, haven’t you sent me that? do you need our support? Do you want us to set priorities? What are you on? Do you understand? But I try to control this thing, like no, no, not the time, not calling every time, knowing if they are at home or not, but that ting, like weekly goals” (interview n°13)*

Results management: *“a lot of confidence, a lot of confidence. In fact, we have a meeting every Friday to check how we did and to see what the next steps are. And in that meeting we see the results. In fact, the supervision is through me always calling my direct boss, who sometimes is in and others out, but when he is in, he participates. So, he is taking notes, and you note if there are progresses or not” (interview n°16).*

“What she did [the interviewed is speaking about his direct boss] was to give a structure to each one of us’ tasks, the area resources with timelines, what to deliver, tasks, deadlines, and that is super positive because we focused our job pursuing that goal and that is the way, we think. Obviously, that is what we did in our area, I do not know if the others do the same [...] but at least we have had incredibly good results. In this sense, now [...] I am in charge of the team, I am not calling each one of them. All of them know their responsibilities. Maybe they knows what their tasks are too, what they have to be doing during this period, where there must not be any disorder even though your boss is not there now” (interview n°4).

Feedback: *“You know what? If I have to be critical, I have received better reviews or better evaluations working in a remote way than when I worked in person. For example, if today you are doing it right, you are in the right way. It means that, they have increased their efficiency level, it has been good. I have had good reviews. And it was not like that when I worked in person. Now [...] they test you more, or they make better... sur, like they give you more feedback about your work, so you know you are doing it ok, or you know you are doing it wrong” (interview n°6).*

Due to the fact that the management results and the goal-oriented work are the central topics that the remote leadership looks for, in an organization that for the first time is trying this new labor agreement starts to arise new control and work management measures associated with the goal of making things happen, which forces the realization of teamwork periodic meetings and data download, as a part of the remote work methodologies that have been implemented in the organization:

New control measures and work management: *“Interviewed: But there you have to play with the topic prioritization, also at some time we started to do something, like, something that we as a department did not have, it was uhm... each of us had our own topics, but deep down, as I saw there was so much uncertainty, we started to bring something like a topic whiteboard, somehow.*

Interviewer: so, you are telling me you developed a tool to be able to... manage your work? I do not know if that is the right word.

Interviewed: Manage our work! Yeah, to manage our work! Because we had a topic whiteboard with all topics on it and then we decided a timeline for each topic, so that we could see how much time everyone had, in order to not be overwhelmed by the deadlines, somehow” (interview n°1).

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Making things happen: *“Interviewed: Yes, I believe so. How can I say it... how can I say it, they realize it, because you are not there anymore, I mean, you are still doing your work, and everyone can tell, because it becomes obvious that the job is done anyway [...] is just that in my case, my position is like this I have to be available all day without exemptions, but as I said before, it is an organization issue. No, because when I started as a supervisor, I had people calling me all day. But after a while it did not happen again, and that is where I started to manage my time and I knew that some things needed to be done earlier every day. So that is the reason I, I do not know, am working right now. Now I start my turn at seven and at three and a half I should be ready and if there is anything to see, those are specific topics. Nothing more, it is not that complicated”* (interview n°11).

Teamwork periodic meetings: *“Personally, I have always received support from my bosses. I have not felt under pressure, nor doing something wrong due to the lack of time. That is why I was telling you about that sometimes, when you have children is harder. In that sense, I could not say that my bosses were not in my shoes. [...] no, no, I do not have that experience, actually is exactly the opposite. I mean, they have been worried about us all the time. We have always had weekly meetings where they would always ask how our family was, how were things going with everything and everybody at home. You could see their worriedness”* (interview n°7).

To name some digital or remote leadership properties, we found elements themselves about the closeness between this leader and each particular member, just like the whole group itself, something that in the theoretical dimension of “organizational communication” we call “closeness due to the distance”. In this sense, the labor recognition opportunities are profoundly important, in the same way that the feedback chances, to create the commitment and the members identification with the group and the organization goals, which is the key for the correct performance of the remote work, because every member is aware of their individual, team and organizational goals which allow them to adjust their tasks and functions according to them. Also, another important characteristic of this leadership style shows the relation with the encouragement of remote recreative activities, to connect people out of their labor spaces (informal), increasing even more the “closeness due to the distance” and the teamwork:

Labor recognition: *“I mean, we feel like we have worked a lot more from home rather than we were in the office. So, in that way we can measure ourselves and know what is our daily job without the need of a supervisor in our heads telling us hey, what happened to this? You have not done that yet; you are late here! The truth it is the opposite, the times we have had general meetings with our bosses have gone great and they have congratulated us [and corrected us] in some specific items [...]”* (interview n°14).

“Actually, that communication, I always... I used to focus on the person, just by giving it a name, but is different to do it with one person than with more people, because deep down when there are more people you feel more powerful, that is my vision, the person feels encouraged because is your feedback added to the one coming from the other one” (interview n°1).

Remote recreative activities: *“Interviewed: we made a Bingo where the whole group participated.*

Interviewer: how was that? Tell me how did you do that, how did you organize it, where was it, where the idea came from?

Interviewed: telework, each one of us at their home, uhm, uhm, some coworker who is good at ITs organized it, he sent bingo cards out for everyone, and he was the one... well, as always he is one of the guys who organize things or move people to do new staffs, at the end we all follow him. So, he was in charge of organize it, but we all participated, people from Management until the last client” (interview n°18).

Not to lose connection with people: *“There came a time in which, to not lose that connection between us, even if we could communicate internally, we kept it as a team, we did it every day. We got along almost every day uhm, to talk for a while about labor topics, though it was normally on Fridays, it was just conversation, and it was strategical because we set the meeting around noon, in that way the meeting would be over by one thirty or two o’clock. If someone had a topic it would be discussed, otherwise they would just exit the meeting”* (interview n°1).

Teamwork: *“of course, at the end this is a chain, and my part must be as good as can be so that my afternoon coworker gets to do his part for the guy who comes at night and so on. So, if I stop to do my part, obviously I am letting a work overload for my coworker, and he will do the same to the guy after. It is a chain, so, what we all need to do is our job and try to help each other”* (interview n°12).

The digital leadership dimension is a crucial piece in the GT about the TCH effects on the labor performance, because the leader ability to make easier the incorporation of the IT, the closeness encouragement, the results management, have a direct effect on

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the labor performance and the position functions fulfillment, and it can be a positive result if the digital leadership has those characteristics, as much as a negative result if the leadership cannot add these characteristics to its group directing styles.

6. Base factors and condition to the function's development in a remote way.

This dimension is directly related to the material and/or the work environment aspects that each person has in the place where its remote work is performed, along with the responsibilities that must be taken at home, which act as distractors and/or intervenient factors affecting the job development when they are present, as much as the individual, self-learned and self-management skills, it is possible to identify among them that those workers with previous remote work experiences (in other jobs or activities) have a better base condition for the right development of their functions. Nevertheless, the amount of people who announced having previous experiences were the less:

Favorable conditions: *"there is not much to do. I mean, here in the house, thank God I have my mom's help and I do not have to do chores; I do not have to clean up, I do not have to do the dishes, I do not have to cook, I do not have to make my bed, I do not do anything but work then. I am so lucky, I know it, so the topic of time and boredom took me to stay more time focused on what I had to do for work"* (interview n°14).

"I isolated one of the rooms, I turned it into an office. I set all the needed conditions to be able to work quiet and comfortably, then I changed it again because it was getting colder. Well, winter came in, I went inside. Ah, and now I am comfortable here, without cold, without heat. I do not know, getting along with it. How did I manage to do that? Uhm, I locked myself in, for example, trying to stay away from the yelling, I do not know, the car outside making noise, I do not know, from all the noise coming from a normal community. Uhm, you isolate yourself, you do that, and you just focus, like now at the meeting" (interview n°16).

Previous telework experience: *"Interviewer: so, this is not your first telework experience?"*

Interviewed: *No, no, because at some time I worked on site, in a room, supporting with... also as a buyer, but mostly supporting a specific room with inaugurations or staff like that. So how I now how to do it [referring to her previous experience], it was not complicated to develop this job"* (interview n°18).

Self-management: *"Yes, because generally if there is work to do, uhm... for example, when I work on mornings... now I have the afternoon turn, now I am working, but I keep working, I take the time to advance on the job, I take the time to organize myself, to say until ... I have to get something done until nine, so then I can go with this, so then I can have a snack, and I take the opportunity to feed my baby too"* (interview n°9).

"No, generally this has not been an issue for me, because you have to keep adjusting yourself to every situation. One has to be a person in that sense, super self-learner just like trying to fit in, let's say, in the most possible ways. I mean, one, cannot be, let's say, with a negative mind and hoping the things fall out from the sky. Is exactly the opposite, on has to be proactive here, and if you are not overloaded with work, try to find some alternative to have something to do, right? I, since the new telework modality began, I knew that there is always something to do, and the truth is I feel this was well managed" (interview n°10).

In the material or infrastructure topic conditions, is extremely important to have or to generate a fitting working place, which can reunite the minimum requirements so that the worker can focus on the development of his functions at home. Related to the IT base condition to the correct development of telework, a good internet connection is a must, just as we said it in the technological aspects dimension:

Material aspects, having a space to work: *"actually, this is complex, because deep down, you were the one fitting in this case, finally you had to be in a space like this office, you have to have your space. So, this popped out of a trial-and-error situation. In my case I found out that truly I was not doing my best. It came a time, maybe after a month where I felt like ay! I am here every day, and I am not doing much! That was my way of thinking during the first month. Actually, I am so missing the point, I do not have my own space to work. That was one of the issues. So, that is on the collaborator. Maybe in this case if there was a telework modality, the company would have to give you access to a whole desk, a comfortable work chair, etc. in my case I had to discover that it was the minimum, but it was not an issue for you before because the office was adapted to it. Of course, I do not know if the internet provision is a must, because today if you do not have wi-fi access is like you do not even exist, you are no one in the world. I do not know if I answered your question, but for me, all you have to do is to configure your workspace, and you have to know that is not an obligation to have it if you are not used to work from home"* (interview n°1).

"Yes, the truth is that I, really, just as you say, have a really good perception, I even feel privileged because I have a space in my house to work, a room with a door lock that I adapted as my office and not bother anyone" (interview n°20).

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Another important aspect in this dimension, is particularly relate to the characteristics of the functions developed by workers, which we have pointed out have been widened, not only to analytics functions or knowledge workers (telework friendly), but to administrative and repetitive (*case workers*) functions which are not incompatible with telework:

Telework supported functions: *“Uhm, first of all, there is not anymore the trip from my house to the warehouse, that was one hour by bus, that is the first thing that pops out, the commodity of not having to get up at five o’clock in the morning, take a shower and get ready to get into the van and travel. Uhm, the same amount of time than now. I am a vegetarian, and it was an issue at the warehouse, for example, if I had to choose between eating pasta with no sauce and cooking something nice for myself changes the whole thing for me, I spend more time at my house, I am more relaxed too, I am relaxed. For example, I am working on my desk chair, which is much more comfortable than the work I am used to, because as I said, how now I work from a PC, and what I do rarely is shared with more people. It was like moving my office into my house, in an even more comfortably space and totally different if I had to work with people constantly and in person. For example, Diego has to work at the warehouse, he has no choice. He cannot change the work he has for one in a remote way. But if my job does not need to be at the warehouse, is like used space. For example, on Monday I stepped by to say hello, “Hello, how are you?” “hi, hi, hi, hi. Then I sat down and said, oh no, there is not time to do anything, so I kept myself greeting everyone” (interview n°2).*

Interviewer: *according to your tasks in the remote work modality, can you develop all your duties in a remote way, or you have to stood by sometimes, for example, to go to the distribution center or to some specific place?*

Interviewed: *No, I cannot. You will see, I can perform all my job in a remote way. Even if when we were at the distribution center we could, maybe, go down and check one or two pending things, maybe to optimize the process. I do telework as well, I do it in the same way as before. My job has not changed much” (interview n°6).*

Summarizing, the positive factors and conditions to the development of their functions in this remote modality are linked to the material or infrastructure aspects, the worker’s roles or responsibilities at home, and the properties themselves of the position functions, and while those keep related to analytic and IT management aspects, better it will be for the remote performance.

7. Unpromising factors and condition to the function’s development in a remote way.

The theoretical dimension related to the “unpromising factors and conditions” is one of the most complex dimensions according to the number of characteristics and properties that make it. It is corelated with the multiple TCH distracting elements. Among the diversity of elements that gives shape and sense to this dimension, we can find some material or infrastructure aspects, organizational aspects (related to the work culture, the organizational communication, etc.), the distractors and home interferences, along with the extra labor responsibilities that workers have to deal with being at home:

Material aspects/ one same place for everything: *“At the beginning, it was a hundred percent of uncertainty. Not knowing how this was going to last. Not knowing if I had or not to prepare a workspace, if I had to invest or not into set a place. At first, while surfing that uncertainty, it felt hard. I live in an apartment and get up, go out of bed or get out of the shower, get to the living room and be there until eight o’clock in the evening to go back to bed, felt a little monotonous and boring, until I made the decision of creating a workspace” (interview n°17).*

Organizational/cultural aspects: *“In fact, it was presumed that if you were not there [at the office] you were at Cerro el Plomo [is where the corporative offices are] or you were not working. But there was not the presumption that you were working from home. And the structure was not friendly with it too, I think. No, because, for example if we go to a meeting, if you were at home, you would just miss the meeting. You were not there, then the telework culture did not exist [...]. Also, this is a mainly meetings company, so you have to have the culture about how to manage the meetings, knowing that some of them will be physically and others in a remote way” (interview n°7).*

“Uhm... no, is just not... is like... like the kid who sometimes cries, and you do not know why he cries, and you have to pay attention to him, and you have to send an e-mail, and with only one hand. If you do not know why he is crying... you have to pay attention to him, because he needs his mom. Though, you can write with only one hand, I learnt how to do that” (interview n°9).

The difficulties to develop the functions in a remote way are also related to the adaptation process lived by the workers, acknowledging this as the first remote work experience. Along with it, we found some aspects of the functions themselves developed by the people in the organization, which cannot be fully developed in a remote way. Nevertheless, the urgency derived from the pandemic and the need of keeping the workers safe, along with the need of keeping the business running, implied that some positions, whose functions are totally administrative and are used to a specific work journey, have started to run in a remote

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way and they had added some more elements or tasks over the time, so they could keep working in the TCH way, at least during the hardest stage of the Covid-19 Pandemic in Chile:

Telework incompatible functions: *“The relationship with people is super important to our position’s duties. I mean, for example, when here we attend people, we understand their problems or we can figure what could have been missing, for example for a remuneration or because the person was out. And you also have the relationship with the supervisors and the bosses of these people. So, you have the closeness to ask: hey, why he did not come? And you do not have to be calling out the phone; many times, they are in a meeting or cannot answer, etc. so, when you are with them in the same place or in the same office, or in the same center, you can get information more quickly. I mean, being at home, if someone does not answer you, you cannot go to their house or their office looking for them. Instead, when working on site you have the opportunity if they do not answer you, you can go and look for them physically”* (interview n°5).

“At first, the truth is that I would go three times a week, and I was there all day, it means arrive early and leave late at night, uhm... we are saying eleven at night and eleven and a half at night, and the next day you have to keep going. And more than that it was made in order to do things right and to not have any trouble, because we were just starting with this new modality, from movement to quietness. So, I used to go three times a week and the other two days I used to work from home and adding Saturdays and Sundays because my job is 24/7. So yeah, uhm, it is like, it is complicated to be between your house and your work” (interview n°19).

As a result of the unpromising conditions, we found different effects or impacts on the performance levels self-received and reported by the workers. One important characteristic of those effects is that, to keep the same labor performance when comparing to the period when they were at the office, has had a bigger cost when speaking of effort due to the increased work overload and the family-work interferences (by the mess between the administrative telework elements themselves and the environment elements themselves and the home responsibilities), so this cost has to consider too the total amount of time given to work:

Increased overload and work effort: *“it was more the work overload, is just, look, more than anything, I keep falling in the same place, but it is because being here [meaning being at the employer office] you used to do everything directly and you had the solutions right away, I do not know, if you needed something, you would go to the place and solve it”* (interview n°7).

“Of course not, no, because the mental effort is the same. Is the same as usual, of course there are some observations, like for example, the movement of the people, you end up using your head more than usual, because, at the end my job does not end at five thirty in the afternoon. My job ends at eleven at night, at eleven thirty. But I, in that time space I have my free time uh, why? Because the night shift people have to be at 10:30 pm in the distribution center. I have to be around my phone in case we have some issues, so, uhm, deep down we keep ourselves working. I keep myself working, I am never free, and at the next day I have to keep working in the same way” (interview n°19).

To dedicate more time to work: *“So, in that sense, when you are at your home, is like you are more stressed, because you have to be worried about the time. Sometimes, for example, there were many times where I did not have lunch at the right time, I had lunch around six because I did not have time before that, because I had too much work”* (interview n°10).

“Interviewer: have you ever had to dedicate more time to complete your tasks or is it similar to the time it used to take you when you worked in person?”

Interviewed: I dedicate more time to work now than before.

Interviewer: Now, during telework?

Interviewed: Now, yes, yes, now. I work during more time in this modality” (interview n°6).

Summarizing, the unpromising factors, and conditions to the correct performance of people’s functions in a remote way are related to the material aspects (not having a workspace), the organizational aspects such as the kind of labor communication and the culture based on the in-person work and the distractions coming from the FIW. We can add to these factors the fact that this was the first telework experience for most workers, which is why this adaptation process implied a learning curve and performance adaptation. The administrative functions, characterized by the development of repetitive tasks and in the timeframe of a defined schedule (office hours), are unpromising with telework, as much as the labors reach higher efficiency levels than when working in person. While this work in a remote way, shows a lack of efficiency due to the need of incorporation of different communication media to obtain information and to coordinate people different tasks, which implies that the work takes longer until it is done. If it is true, the organization did not have any efficiency loss over the task’s development (labor performance), due to the fact that the workers kept themselves fulfilling their responsibilities. Nevertheless, the cost associated to the efficiency loss implied the time dedicated to work grew and it was taken by the workers even when it was affecting their life quality and their physical and

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mental health (Venegas Tresierra & Leyva Pozo, 2020b). This is why, we point out that there is not recommended to kept administrative workers in a remote work way.

8. Remote work positive effects.

The convergence of the theoretical dimensions present in the grounded theory creates ambiguities on the self-perceived labor performance effects, as much as in other dimensions of the organizational behavior (leadership, culture, and communication), and these can be positive or negative according to the base factors, the characteristics of the position itself and the characteristics of the infrastructure conditions. In this we will focus on analysis of the TCH experience positive effects inside the organization. When speaking about the TCH modality's direct benefits, we can identify the regular benefits of this remote work modality associated to the decreased movement times, associated to the trips from home to work and vice versa, the work-family conciliation and, one new dimension proper to the Covid-19 pandemic context; to be able to protect ourselves from the disease spreading.

Not to spend time traveling to the place of work: *“yeah, the thing, well for example, now a days I have to take my son to the kinder garden, I leave him there at seven thirty in the morning. So that means I arrive here to work at eight, but if I were at the office I would be arriving there around nine, because this kinder garden opens at seven thirty, and then I have to face the traffic, get to the distribution center, I would be there around eight thirty... nine in the morning, not before”* (interview n°18).

Work-family Conciliation: *“Yes, of course. The contact and communication with my family and with my partner has been affected for this situation. The good thing about this is that today I do not work more than before. I have my time schedule clearer. I can tell you now that I get up almost two hours later than when I used to work in Ciudad de los Valles, I live in San Miguel, it used to take me about one hour and a half to come back home. Now a days, that hour has turned into 10 minutes by car to reach my grandmother's house and share with my mom and grandma one day a week, things that I have never done before”* (interview n°7).

To protect ourselves of the Covid-19 disease spreading: *“I mean, on the first day obviously, when this scenario came on, the pandemic, well, the first measure was the telework for everyone, because we used to work in a physical place. Where maybe, the social isolation issue would not be respected and as a consequence of it we could have had many sick people. I believe we have felt close to the organization in that sense, they have always been there for us”* (interview n°4).

The benefits perceived by the workers in a higher uncertainty context, as much in the sanitary side as in the labor side, implied that people would consider this telework experience as a benefit:

Telework is a benefit: *“I remember what he has been through. Is a way of, I do not know if I should resume this, but is kind of keeping us save and healthy, that is how I understood it. Trying to avoid that rode to the distribution center, to the office. I think this is how I took it”* (interview n°6),

“Sure, me, for example, I have been through all! Hahaha, it has been stressful at times and at times it has not. And uhm, how do I tell you? It helped me a lot. It is that just in this period, I had to... my twins were born, so I had to be there, and this was like a favor to me, being here, doing my telework. At the end this is an advantage for me” (interview n°11).

“I have to feed my baby, mom this, do you understand? But... but I have made good use of this and for me, it, the telework, came in a very goodtime, just the right time, because I had no one to take care of Cata. I had just started that work and I had to coordinate with my boyfriend who will take care of here, but then it changed, he switched his job, and we did not have that chance again, so the telework came just in the right time” (interview n°12).

One direct consequence of the telework benefits and, along with it, to feel like the telework is a benefit, is the fact that workers show a bigger organizational commitment and bigger labor satisfaction, which ends in a motivation to give back what the company gives to them by letting them perform their activities in a remote way:

Increased labor commitment: *“But no, no, not for me, there was no real problem, is just that the responsibility of your position, and the commitment of, let's say, giving worth to the company, to everything, let's say, we committed to everyday tasks of the company”* (interview n°4).

“Yes, in fact I believe so. Uhm, now there is a little bit more of responsibilities, but, but good because I like challenges. And that is the important, try to help, to get over these things, of the bad moments, specially over the fights. Try to help, uh? That tells a lot about yourself, because one let's say, one wants to do its job the best possible way” (interview n°10).

“No, I do not see it, I feel it like you have to have too much control of yourself to not go to sleep, to not say “today I'll stay in bed”. It happens a little, but you have to be really mature. There is a lot of maturity and a sense of responsibility. Totally,

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because if you know you are committed you have to keep your word, you definitely have to do it, no matter where you are” (interview n°14).

Labor satisfaction: “In my labor performance, look, I feel like I have done things better than before, a lot much better. Why? Because I try to thank what they gave me, the opportunity of being at home, then... this. Look, I am going to have been here for a year, my son is one year and three months old. So practically, I went back after the post-natal and three days later they sent me home, so uhm, I think I should be thankful. They sent me a brand-new phone, a new cellphone... a new computer, so, what can I complain of? I have a salary... that remains the same, so, what else?” (interview n°9).

Redistributing the telework benefit: “Now a days, due to the telework modality, we have received all the needed support. For example, from HHRR, each one of the benefits, the implemented electronic signature, that was one too and we did a lot of things, I do not remember all of them right now, but somehow, they make us a part of it, to be more involved with it, with what the company gives us, and also to respond to them. I mean, this is a mutual benefit” (interview n°4).

“Yeah sure, you make more efforts, the fact that...you have to redistribute what you are doing, what they are offering you, what they are giving to you. But it is on me this effort, it is not that someone is asking for it, I want to do it, no one has asked me to” (interview n°9).

The direct effect of this perception of the telework as a benefit from the company has in consequence the increased performance quality perceived by the workers:

Better labor performance: “Interviewer: for example, if you have to evaluate in a 1 to 10 scale, where 1 is too little and 10 is a lot, when speaking about the fulfillment of your tasks, how would you grade your performance? How would you grade the sensation of having completed your duties during telework?”

Interviewed: I would grade it with a 10 because I did everything they asked me for, I am really good. Is true! Hahahaha, everything they asked for, I did it.

Interviewer: do you feel you did it good?

Interviewed: yes, I did. No one never told me to come here. Every time I knew I could not complete my tasks from home I came here, because I had a goal, and I met that goal” (interview n°1).

“In my case, about the things I normally do and solving things that I could not solve at work. Basically, is how they checked it, I had an unsolved problem, and I could not solve it in all day, it just did not work until I arrived home and I was here, this happens a lot. But I just had that way of working. When I am here at home, is basically, like my mind works better, I would say it happens faster, I work faster [...] to be able to develop my job at home, which is working at my desk, in my PC, working, analyzing what I do, what is going on, the CDs and related to that I generate a report or some indicators. Basically, this is my job” (interview n°2).

9. Remote work negative effects.

In the dynamics of the ambiguous results or effects of the TCH reported by the organization members, we found a bigger responsibility perception and the increase in the pressure as a consequence of being working in a remote way, which is also associated with the many activities people do at their houses and that do not belong to the labor itself. The overwhelming perception of being available all the time to solve work issues was one of the aspects told by the workers. This perception is also related to the increase in the time used to work, the work overload and the effort made to complete their functions (as the ones we saw in the dimension: “Unpromising factors and condition to the function’s development in a remote way”):

Bigger responsibility to be in telework: “Let’s say that we, who are in telework, are privileged somehow when comparing with the people working in person, because I think in some way the fact of being in a telework modality is a responsibility, I think it is even bigger than working in person, because you feel like you are under pressure, or you also can feel chased. At the beginning it happen to me that I used to feel chased” (interview n°4).

Multiple functions: “Well, well, the first was the internet issue, that has been like... (laughs), but uhm, the mom side, to forget about staff, to remember some others. To understand that now I am working from home and to forget my mom role of being worried about everything around me, we have to see this, I have to fix that, uhm I have to make lunch, uhm? Is like to take that chip off, the one that rules your normal life. Going to the office, coming back home and there you knew that when you arrived home your job was done, you disconnect yourself from work when you arrive home, you are not all the time in the computer. So then, when you get home you become again into a mom, and that was hard, to understand that now is different. And the focusing, to be able to focus on what you are doing and not be aware about your environment” (interview n°19).

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To be able all the time: *“Of course, it was super uncomfortable because you had to be close to your phone all the time, so uhm I was having lunch and I was all the time with my cellphone, why? Because I could get some message or a call. But when I work in person that does not happen, you are not online all the time. I did not have this insecurity. I do not know if I should call it insecurity, but it is like a feeling that you want to be available all the time, so they are sure you are not doing anything else, something like that, I do not know. For example, my boss calls me at some time and says what are you doing? No, I am making lunch, uhm ok, but [...] I asked you this and ...but hey! I have to make lunch!” (interview n°13).*

The dynamic of elements that increase the pressure on the worker during the TCH, leads to negative consequences such as work overload and stress, creating a negative experience about remote work and showing a decrease in the labor performance:

Negative consequences: *“The truth is that I set the living-dining area to be able to work at home. And until now is a constant argument with my family. I mean, they still cannot understand that this is a 24/7 job, we have people working in three shifts, they can call you any time and that is more or less what is hard to understand. In my case, uhm, though now is less than before, at the beginning it was so hard for them, they wanted me to go shopping some groceries, or going out with them all the time, but no, I could not. And now I tell them ‘that day I am going to work until late at night’ or ‘that day I have all this work’ uhm? Particularly the telework topic was a lot. A lot of disagreements, arguments. I do not even have the time to have dinner sometimes. I just cannot. Uhm, I cannot have lunch at the same time my family does. So, they got this wrong idea that I was disliking them or that my work was more important for me than them. So, I also had to fix that with my family uhm, over all because I... I mean in that time my father was suspended from work. He used to work out of Santiago, so after being travelling all the time to have to spend all his time at home and see me at home everyday without us sharing time like he would have liked it, was a little frustrating” (interview n°5).*

Work overload: *“Interviewed: despite the fact that us as a team meet together once a week and do our job and everything I feel like the teamwork, I mean my department, we are two people. I think it has not been enough, but it is because that I have had to be in charge of many things, many responsibilities that were someone else’s, bout how I am the head of the area, at the end I prefer to do it all by myself. That is one of my weaknesses. I prefer not to ask because I know maybe it won’t be done, so I prefer to do the job myself and not ask someone else.*

Interviewer: and in that sense, that work overload you are doing, how would you qualify your performance on this additional work? I mean, as you say, it is not your duty, but because you are the head of the area you have to accept the challenge and do it anyway.

Interviewed: Well, the truth is that I try to do it, but not well enough. And I do it poorly because I have so much work to do” (interview n°3).

Decrease in the labor performance: *“Interviewer: these difficulties you are talking about, have they had any impact on your functions performance?*

Interviewed: uhm look, when we started teleworking between March and April, uhm, I felt like I did not have enough time to finish my work. Despite de fact that I was online all day, I felt there was no time. It was shown in a huge number of processes, as we call them. I needed time to upload something, I needed time to review another [...] I mean, if you feel overwhelmed for being at home, it obviously has an impact on your labor performance” (interview n°5)

“Interviewer: Well, that is one of the things I wanted to ask you. If you analyze the experience of this last year working in a remote way, how has it impacted your labor performance?

Interviewed: I think my level has decreased a little, I mean I am still working a lot, I am a perfectionist by nature and when I am working [she means when she work at her office in the company] at my office, of course I am more focused, I have no distractions, here at home is my daughter and that is a distraction that is not in my office” (interview n°12).

Grounded theory about the TCH effects on the labor performance.

The studied organization went through a inevitable and improvised process, related to the urgency of implementing new remote work measures to a group of workers who develop analytics and administrative functions. The organization went through an organizational learning process that we call “learning to sail on telework”. This adaptation process, characterized by trial-error work, created new learnings and adaptations in the digital leadership, IT development and digital skills on the organization members dimensions.

There is an ambiguous impact (negative/positive) of the TCH on the labor performance directly associated with variables such as: kind of task or position in the company and factors given from the environment where TCH takes place. In this sense, the performance perception of the members of the organization who participate in the TCH has been positive for the group of people who claims to have the minimal infrastructure and IT conditions as well as those who develop analytic jobs.

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In other aspects, the TCH experience is a negative experience for those people who develop administrative, rutinary functions focused on tasks and processes that are developed in an efficient way if they are at the usual place of work, but in the remote way their work ended up being less efficient, which is translated into a bigger labor effort. Also, those workers who have incorrect infrastructure, internet, and IT conditions to develop their functions from home, feel like the TCH has impacted in a negative way on their labor performance. On the same way, the workers who show a higher grade of family-work and work-family interference, share the same perception.

Illustration 1: The effects of TCH on job performance (own elaboration).

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the following sections we will compare the main findings of the investigation with the recent literature, which talks about the remote work effects in the pandemic context. Particularly, we will talk about the organizational learning aspects, the performance perceived by the workers who develop administrative functions and the ambiguous results of the labor performance (positive and negative).

Organizational learning: the organization went through a learning process, which is the topic of the main category called “learning to sail on telework”, this is characterized by a trial-error focusing that created some adaptations in the “digital leadership”, IT aspects and digital skills dimension on the organization members, along with an adjustment of the organizational communication. Whether the literature about the WFH effects on the covid-19 pandemic context does not make a direct reference about the organizational learning, they implicitly refer some adaptations and learnings, as much in an individual level as in a collective level, that popped out in the pandemic context. On the individual aspects appear the specific skills, work/personal life balance and better labor performance development (Dima et al., 2019). On the collective aspects, it is possible to note the double benefit of remote work, related to a increase in the workers security and the business continuity on times of crisis (Belzunegui-Eraso & Erro-Garcés, 2020). Due to the fact that the organizational learning is not something clearly announced on the recent research, the developed substantial theory gives new hints to a new dimension to understand and to explain the TCH effects.

Labor performance on workers with administrative functions: the administrative functions, focused on the repetitive tasks’ development and a defined time schedule frame (office hours) are not compatible with telework, due to the fact that those are activities that reach higher levels of efficiency when are done in person. While, doing their tasks in a remote way, they show a decrease in their efficiency due to the fact that they must add different communication media to be able to obtain and coordinate the tasks information with different people, which implies that the job takes more time to be done. If so, the organization did not lose efficiency on the tasks’ development (labor performance), because the workers continued performing their responsibilities, the cost of the efficiency lose implied an increase in the time destined to work which was assumed by the workers who sacrificed their life quality and their physical and mental health, creating a perception of an increase in the work burden and, along with it, an increase in the personal effort to complete the tasks.

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Related to the WFH expansion phenomenon, related to the administrative functions, it is possible to note negative effects on the labor performance, the life quality of workers and the work/personal life balance (Thulin et al., 2019a). Along with it, negative psychological effects are shown, such as mental fatigue and work overload, derived from some kind of functions which are not suitable to develop in a remote way, just like the isolation effects themselves (Venegas Tresierra & Leyva Pozo, 2020b).

Our findings are consistent with the recent investigation results. We establish that the organization must evaluate the continuity of the remote work for the administrative functions, because the evidence shows that is not sustainable to keep those in time.

If this is not a causal investigation, the authors McGregor and Doshi (2020) give some findings of this phenomenon. In their research they point out that the motivation and performance show a decrease in long terms related to two key variables, which are present in the studied organization. The first one is related to the impossibility of choosing the work modality by the worker, affecting a lot their motivation. In fact, the TCH does not allow these flexibilities, according to the health and legislative conditions. Nevertheless, it is necessary that the coming decisions in this matter promote a good environment where the worker can choose where, how, and when to work. This adjustment would have a significant impact on the personal wellbeing and in the labor performance. The second one, described by McGregor and Doshi (2020), tells us about the WFH effect on those repetitive, administrative, and operational functions, defined by the authors as “tactical performance workers”. The findings show that to perform this kind of duties in a remote way, generates a natural decrease in the motivation and commitment, negatively impacting the labor performance. This is precisely related to some of the findings of this research, by noting that this kind of tasks requires a bigger communication and coordination between the teams, and also the contact reduction negatively impacts on this kind of functions. To abuse of this tactical performance makes people stop solving problems and thinking creatively, and instead they tend to do the minimal.

As a suggest for the people management in the organizations, we think would be good to implement elements from the “adaptative performance” (McGregor and Doshi, 2020), which balances administrative and operational elements with participative activities and that tend to complex and relevant problem solving for teams and the organization. In this sense, the adaptative performance motivates the collaborators to be a part of the solutions to the problems or improvement projects the organization has to face to co-construct creative solutions by incrementing the commitment and reinventing the work by turning it in something relevant for the organization progress. To be able to move into this new work philosophy, it is not only necessary the will to do it, but some practices and a leadership mentality which is focused on people, giving place to people for experimenting and solving problems that really matter. While certain degrees of limits and guidelines help people to move, too many of it creates a vicious sequence of demotivation. If the TCH nature remains being mostly orientated to tasks and without space for the adaptative performance, mixing the impact on the people’s wellbeing, is possible to announce a decrease in the performance in medium term.

Ambiguous results (positive and negative): the findings of the investigations show that, related to the base elements that make possible the functions development in a remote way, along with the implementation degree of the aspects relatives to the leadership, the communication and IT, results are generated on the labor performance that can be as positive as negative, which implies a TCH ambivalence due to the present conditions as much in an individual level as in a collective level interacting between them.

The recent research about this phenomenon show results that can be a paradox according to the remote work advantages and the disadvantages, because the individual and organizational dimensions reported (performance, work/personal life balance, increased organizational commitment, labor satisfaction, less desertion and creativity increment) may achieve benefits by the telework effects, as it can achieve damage as a consequence of the social isolation (Lampert & Poblete, 2018) and labor (Golden et al., 2008), the material conditions the workers have in the place where the remote work is developed (Bhattacharya & Mittal, 2020) and the blurring lines between the labor journey and personal time (Bhattacharya & Mittal, 2020), all this added to the difficulty to disconnect form work (Thulin et al., 2019) and as a consequence the increased effort to complete the tasks (Spilker, 2014), just to cite the main elements that creates this telework paradox according to its advantages and disadvantages, which fit with our investigations results.

Based on the investigation findings, we establish that the main contribution of this work is related to the approach of the negative effects that are shown in the labor performance as a consequence of the addition of administrative labors to the WFH modality, which can be more efficient when are developed in person instead telework. Along with it, the TCH phenomenon and its ambiguous results is another contribution in a theoretical and conceptual level, in the means that there is a change in the remote work nature by making it more rigid about how, when, and where to develop that job, which is correlated to the administrative functions, along with the pandemic restriction themselves.

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REFERENCES.

- 1) Aigner, M. (2012). Teoría Fundada: ¿arte o ciencia? *Centro de Estudios de Opinión*, 1–14. <http://aprendeenlinea.udea.edu.co/revistas/index.php/ceo/article/viewFile/1632/1285>
- 2) Aliaga, O., Cofré, D., & Soto, R. (2021). Working homebound and its effects on performance and work productivity during the times of Covid-19. *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research and Review*, 03(05), 1207–1215. <http://journalijisr.com/issue/working-homebound-and-its-effects-performance-and-work-productivity-during-times-covid-19>
- 3) Belzunegui-Eraso, A., & Erro-Garcés, A. (2020). Teleworking in the context of the Covid-19 crisis. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(9), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12093662>
- 4) Bhattacharya, S., & Mittal, P. (2020). The impact of individual needs on employee performance while teleworking1. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 14(5), 63–85. <https://doi.org/10.14453/aabfj.v14i5.5>
- 5) Bosua, R., Gloet, M., Kurnia, S., Mendoza, A., & Yong, J. (2013). Telework, productivity and wellbeing. *Telecommunications Journal of Australia*, 63(1), 1–12.
- 6) Chávez, J. D. (2020). Entendiendo el teletrabajo. *Universidad Politécnica Territorial Del Estado Aragua*, April.
- 7) Chiavenato, I. (2009). *Comportamiento organizacional. La dinámica del éxito en las organizaciones*. McGraw-Hill.
- 8) Conejo, F. (2020). Teletrabajo Asistido en los tiempos del Coronavirus (COVID-19). *Tecnología Vital*, 2(8).
- 9) Data UC. (2021). *Visualizador covid-19 Chile*. Resumen Nacional. <https://coronavirus.mat.uc.cl>
- 10) Dima, A. M., Tuclea, C. E., Vrănceanu, D. M., & Tigu, G. (2019). Sustainable social and individual implications of telework: A new insight into the Romanian labor market. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(13). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11133506>
- 11) Gobierno de Chile. (2021). *Estrategia gradual paso a paso*. Chilereports.Cl. <https://chilereports.cl/noticias/2020/08/11/estrategia-gradual-paso-a-paso>
- 12) Hernández Sampieri, R., Fernández Collado, C., & Baptista Lucio, M. (2014). *Metodología de la investigación* (Sexta). McGraw-Hill.
- 13) InvestChile. (2020). *Estudio en Chile: El 95% de las empresas ha implementado teletrabajo*. <http://blog.investchile.gob.cl/bloges/estudio-en-chile-el-95-de-las-empresas-ha-implementado-teletrabajo>
- 14) Lozada Elizalde, L. C. (2016). El Teletrabajo: Una modalidad de trabajo eficiente que se impone como tendencia global. In *Universidad Militar Nueva Granada*.
- 15) McGregor L., & Doshi N. (2020). How to keep your team motivated, remotely. *Harvard Business Review*, <https://hbr.org/2020/04/how-to-keep-your-team-motivated-remotely>
- 16) Mann, S., & Holdsworth, L. (2003). The psychological impact of teleworking: Stress, emotions and health. *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 18(3), 196–211. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-005X.00121>
- 17) Monasterio Blanco, F. (2021). *Un año de Pandemia en Chile*. Pauta.Cl. <https://www.pauta.cl/nacional/cronologia-primer-ano-pandemia-chile>
- 18) Montt, G., Ordóñez, F., & Silva, I. (2020). *Protección ante la desocupación en Chile Desafíos y oportunidades luego de una crisis sistémica*. https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---americas/---ro-lima/---sro-santiago/documents/publication/wcms_755919.pdf
- 19) Nakrošienė, A., Bučiūnienė, I., & Goštautaitė, B. (2019). Working from home: characteristics and outcomes of telework. *International Journal of Manpower*, 40(1), 87–101. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-07-2017-0172>
- 20) Nicholson, N., & Baruch, Y. (1997). Home, sweet work: Requirements for effective home working. In *Journal of General Management* (Vol. 23, Issue 2, pp. 15–30).
- 21) OIT. (2020). *El teletrabajo durante la pandemia de COVID-19 y después de ella Guía práctica*.
- 22) Raišienė, A. G., Rapuano, V., Varkulevičiūtė, K., & Stachová, K. (2020). Working from home-Who is happy? A survey of Lithuania's employees during the COVID-19 quarantine period. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(13). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12135332>
- 23) Randstad. (2020). *Mercado laboral y coronavirus*. <https://www.trendtic.cl/2020/03/coronavirus-implementacion-de-teletrabajo-en-chile-aumenta-17-veces-entre-fase-1-y-4/>
- 24) Raymond, E. (2005). La teorización anclada (grounded theory) como método de investigación en ciencias sociales: en la encrucijada de dos paradigmas. *Cinta de Moebio: Revista de Epistemología de Ciencias Sociales*, 217–227. <https://www.moebio.uchile.cl/23/raymond.html>

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- 25) Saputra, N., Ardyansyah, F., Madura, U. T., & Thoha, N. (2020). *Tracing the predictors of WFH productivity : A structural equation modelling*. December.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346964489_Tracing_the_predictors_of_WFH_productivity_A_structural_equation_modelling
- 26) Schein, E. (1988). *La cultura empresarial y el liderazgo. Una visión dinámica*. Plaza & Janes Editores S.A.
https://frq.cvg.utn.edu.ar/pluginfile.php/15589/mod_resource/content/0/ScheinLa-Cultura-Empresarial-y-El-Liderazgo.pdf
- 27) Singh, R., Akshay Kumar, M., & Varghese, S. T. (2017). Impact of Working Remotely On Productivity and Professionalism. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 19(5).
- 28) Solís, M. (2017). Moderators of telework effects on the work-family conflict and on worker performance. *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, 26(1). <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJMBE-07-2017-002>
- 29) Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (2002). *Bases de la investigación cualitativa. Técnicas y procedimientos para desarrollar la teoría fundamentada*. Universidad de Antioquia. 31
- 30) Thulin, E., Vilhelmson, B., & Johansson, M. (2019a). New telework, time pressure, and time use control in everyday life. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11113067>
- 31) Thulin, E., Vilhelmson, B., & Johansson, M. (2019b). New telework, time pressure, and time use control in everyday life. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11113067>
- 32) UNED. (n.d.). *Programa de Teletrabajo*. Retrieved February 28, 2021, from <https://www.uned.ac.cr/viplan/teletrabajo/que-es-teletrabajo/historia>
- 33) Vega, R. P., Anderson, A. J., & Kaplan, S. A. (2015). A Within-Person Examination of the Effects of Telework. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 30(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-014-9359-4>
- 34) Venegas Tresierra, C. E., & Leyva Pozo, A. C. (2020a). Fatigue and mental workload among workers: about social distancing | La fatiga y la carga mental en los teletrabajadores: a propósito del distanciamiento social. *Revista Espanola de Salud Publica*, 94.
- 35) Venegas Tresierra, C. E., & Leyva Pozo, A. C. (2020b). Fatigue and mental workload among workers: about social distancing | La fatiga y la carga mental en los teletrabajadores: a propósito del distanciamiento social. *Revista Espanola de Salud Publica*, 94.
- 36) Vyas, L., & Butakhieo, N. (2020). The impact of working from home during COVID-19 on work and life domains: an exploratory study on Hong Kong. *Policy Design and Practice*, 0(0), 1–18.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2020.1863560>
- 37) Willing, C. (2013). *Introducing qualitative research in Psychology* (Tercera ed). Open University Press.